

Quantitative Formulation of Minsky’s Bubble Economy Model

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Abstract—This paper presents a quantitative formulation of Minsky’s bubble economy model to predict price fluctuations in bubble-prone commodities. To represent Minsky’s model, we have utilized the *Planck distribution*, originally describing blackbody radiation.

We develop a quantitative model grounded in the dynamics of the Minsky moment. We fix some parameters of the model using data from Japan and the United States, and apply it to actual transaction price data of Seoul’s real estate market using a single parameter. Using this approach, we forecast the future transaction prices of housing in Seoul.

Moreover, this paper presents predictions regarding the real estate prices, which are currently a matter of concern in South Korea. Utilizing data up to August 2023, the model is trained to forecast the expected real estate prices for the years 2024 and 2025.

I. INTRODUCTION

Commodity prices are primarily determined by supply and demand, but in periods of heightened demand, speculation, or excess liquidity, prices may rise beyond their intrinsic value. When prices continually increase to levels beyond the actual value of the product, it indicates the formation of a price bubble. This phenomenon is well illustrated in Minsky’s Financial Instability Hypothesis, which explains how such unsustainable price increases can occur.

Although Minsky’s model offers qualitative explanations, it lacks the capacity for quantitative predictions regarding the magnitude of bubbles or future price changes. Building on this, a project in 2019 developed a predictive model for Korean housing prices using the *Planck distribution*. This project concluded that there was a bubble in Seoul’s housing market, and as depicted in Fig. 1, predicted a 1.5-fold increase by 2022 (relative to 2018 prices) followed by a crash. While the prediction proved accurate, there were some errors in the scaled data. Additionally, the study utilized data on the Land Price Index rather than direct housing price data. While there is undoubtedly a proportional relationship between the Land Price Index and housing prices, this approach may not be entirely appropriate.

Consequently, after correcting these errors, the same model was reapplied using data up to August 2023 to make further predictions for the current year, 2023.

To quantitatively express the Minsky model, the Planck model was utilized. The Planck model is characterized by its distribution varying in magnitude at specific wavelengths depending on the temperature, and it possesses multiple

Fig. 1: Historical Land Price Index in Seoul (2013–2019)

parameters, making it suitable for fitting the model effectively to the data. In this paper, the frequency of the *Planck distribution* is substituted with time, and an exponential scale is applied to construct the model. The remaining parameters were fixed to values that best fit the data using the gradient descent method.

The rest of this paper consists of the following. First, Sec. II introduces the derivation process of the model along with the method of fitting the data. Then, details on the application are documented in Sec. III. Next, in Sec. V, several results are presented, and finally, a conclusion is given in Sec. VI

II. METHODOLOGY

According to Planck’s Law, the energy of radiation emitted at different frequencies varies depending on the temperature. An examination of the distribution of energy emitted across frequencies at a specific temperature reveals similarities to Minsky’s financial bubble model [1]. The formula for the frequency dependency in the *Planck distribution* is as follows

From the aforementioned formula, one can observe that the shape of the distribution expands with increasing temperature. Additionally, it is conceivable to substitute parameters such as

$$B(\nu, T) = \frac{2h\nu^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{h\nu}{kT}\right) - 1} \quad (1)$$

where h is Planck’s constant, k is Boltzmann’s constant, and c is the velocity of light.

In this formulation, $B(\nu, T)$ represents the spectral radiance, where ν denotes frequency and T indicates temperature. The constants h , c , and k are the Planck constant, the speed of light, and Boltzmann’s constant, respectively. This equation describes the distribution of radiative energy emitted at various frequencies at a given temperature.

Here, h and c , normally physical constants, are substituted with alternative parameters to enhance model flexibility. This modification allows for the application of an exponential

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scale to frequency, transforming it to represent time, akin to the approach in Minsky's model. Consequently, the distribution with five parameters can be defined as follows

$$H(t; a, b, c, d, T) = \frac{e^{at+b}}{\exp\left(\frac{e^{ct+d}}{T}\right) - 1} \quad (2)$$

where t is time, and a, b, c, d are new parameters replacing the original c, h, k .

A. Gradient Descent for the Modified Planck distribution

In Eq.2, it can be seen that the formula can be constructed with five parameters $\vec{p} = (a, b, c, d, T)$ and time t . In this paper, the gradient descent method was used to calculate these five parameters for the data. The method of fitting parameters using the gradient descent approach with MSE as the loss function is as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{p}_{post} &= \vec{p}_{prior} - \alpha \frac{\partial L}{\partial \vec{p}} \\ &= \vec{p}_{prior} + \frac{\alpha}{N} \sum_{i=0}^i (y_i - H(t)_i) \frac{\partial H}{\partial \vec{p}}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here, L represents the loss function (MSE), (t_i, y_i) denotes the observed housing price at time t_i , N is the total number of data points, and α is the learning rate vector for each parameter \vec{p} .

III. FITTING HOUSING PRICE DATA FROM VARIOUS COUNTRIES WORLDWIDE

Numerous countries around the world have exhibited the phenomenon of housing price bubbles. Notably, events such as the subprime mortgage crisis in the United States and the collapse of the real estate bubble in Japan are prominent examples. Furthermore, this phenomenon is not limited to the United States and Japan, as similar trends have been observed in Spain and Ireland as well. The housing price data for each country were sourced from OECD data [2]. Fig.2 illustrates the preprocessing of this data, centering on the points where price bubbles are evident in four selected countries.

A. Preprocessing of International Data

Housing price data were obtained from countries that have exhibited patterns of bubble-inflated housing prices, including the United States, Japan, Ireland, and Spain. This housing price data is considered time series data, encompassing the period from the onset to the end of the abnormal price formation. Furthermore, to account for the factors of housing price increases due to economic growth, the data was adjusted by removing the overall price increase from the start to the endpoint.

$$D_k = \{(t_{k1}, v_{k1}), (t_{k2}, v_{k2}) \cdots (t_{ki}, v_{kN_k})\}, \quad (4)$$

In Eq.4, D_k represents the dataset including k data points varying for each country. $k = \{JP, US\}$ represents the datasets for each respective country: Japan, the United States

of America, Spain, and Ireland. Similarly, N_k is the total number of data points for each country. Where t_{ki} denotes yearly time, and v_{ki} indicates the normalized value of the actual housing price at a given point in time. To facilitate the comparison of multiple datasets, the time intervals have been uniformly scaled as follows

$$\hat{t}_{ki} = (t_{ki} - t_{k1}) * 230 / N_k \quad (5)$$

where \hat{t}_{ki} is the new time scale from t_{ki} and 230 is a scaled arbitrary number for comparing with other datasets. Additionally, considering the impact of economic growth on the rise in housing prices, a linear adjustment has been made to remove this factor from each data point as follows

$$\hat{v}_{ki} = v_{ki} - \frac{(v_{kN_k} - v_{k1_k})}{N_k} i \quad (6)$$

where \hat{v}_{ki} is the rescaled house price index value.

$$\hat{D}_k = \{(t_{k1}, v_{k1}), (t_{k2}, v_{k2}) \cdots (t_{ki}, v_{kN_k})\}, \quad (7)$$

After normalizing data, datasets are redefined as Eq.7 and Fig.2 shows the normalized Housing price value within a similarly normalized time interval.

Fig. 2: Normalized Housing Price Data in Selected Countries

B. Fitting to the Modified Planck distribution

We can fit the housing price data in Eq.7 with the modified *Planck distribution* function using the gradient descent method.

Fig.3 shows the modeled distribution for each country dataset. The fit of the modified *Planck distribution* to the data can be assessed using the R^2 score.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_k} (y_{ki} - \hat{v}_{ki})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_k} (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (8)$$

where R^2 is the coefficient of determination, measuring the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables, \hat{y}_{ki} is the predicted value by the model, and \bar{y} is the mean of the observed data. The model achieved R^2 scores of 0.96

Fig. 3: Fitted Curves for Japanese and U.S. Housing Price Data

(US) and 0.94 (Japan), indicating strong goodness of fit. Furthermore, the parameters a , b , c , and d , excluding T , were fixed at values that yield high R^2 scores for both the American and Japanese datasets.

Consequently, fixing the parameters other than T to the values calculated as $a = \frac{1}{19}$, $b = -1$, $c = \frac{1}{57}$, $d = 7$, results in a quantitative representation of the Minsky model. In this context, T can be interpreted as analogous to the temperature in the *Planck distribution*, where an increase in temperature corresponds to an increase in emitted energy at a specific wavelength. Similarly, in this distribution, T represents the 'heat' of the bubble, indicating the growth of the bubble in the model.

IV. PREDICTING HOUSING PRICES IN SEOUL

In this section, we illustrate the application of the model outlined in Eq.2, incorporating the parameters a , b , c , and d that were established in Section 3, to model the current Transaction Price Index for housing prices in Seoul. The data utilized in this analysis were obtained from the Korea Real Estate Board (REB) under the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, and Transport [3], encompassing monthly data of Seoul's housing Transaction Price Index from 2013 through August 2023.

A. Preprocessing of Seoul Data

The data was scaled in the same manner as in Section 3, aligning the time scale and considering the inflation rate. The inflation rate, averaging 3% from 2013 to 2023, was sourced from the Korean Official Governmental Links (KOGI) [4] under the National Comprehensive Indicator System (index.go.kr). The annual data, calculated as the monthly averages from 2013 through August 2023, are as follows.

$$S = \{v_{s1}, v_{s2}, \dots, v_{si} \dots v_{sN_s}\}, \quad (9)$$

where $N_s = 11$ is the total number of years from 2013 through August 2023. The Transaction Price Index, scaled

to account for the inflation rate, is calculated as follows

$$\hat{v}_{si} = v_{si} - 1.03^i v_{s1}. \quad (10)$$

B. Applying the Model to Fit the Transaction Price Index Data

In this section, the preprocessed data were fitted to the model (Eq.2) using the parameters a , b , c , and d , which were fixed in Subsection III-B. Fig.4 illustrates the forecasting curve obtained from fitting model Eq.2, along with the data. With an R^2 score of 0.95, the curve appears to effectively represent the data. Consequently, the forecasting curve allows for predictions about future changes in housing prices in terms of timing and magnitude.

Fig. 4: Fitted Curve for Seoul Housing Price Transaction Index

V. RESULTS

In Sec.IV-B, we scaled the Seoul Housing Price Transaction Index data and fitted it to Eq.2. Although this model may closely resemble the predictive model from Fig.1 in the Introduction, which was based on 2019 data, we achieved a more accurate fitting model by utilizing precise inflation rates and actual housing price transaction index data. Consequently, we can predict the future magnitude of housing prices based on this curve.

Fig. 5: Forecasted Housing Prices in Seoul (2024–2025)

In Fig. 4, reversing the scaling applied to the inflation rate results in a depiction as shown in Fig.5. By inputting the corresponding time scale values for the years 2024 and 2025 into the model, the predicted prices for these years, relative to 2023, are as follows.

- The annual average housing price in Seoul for 2024 is projected to decrease by 19% compared to the annual average of 2023.

- The annual average housing price in Seoul for 2025 is expected to decrease by 27% compared to the annual average of 2023.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This model was not developed based on any specific economic factors. However, it demonstrates high flexibility in fitting data and consistently yields an R^2 score above 0.9 when applied to different contexts, such as Spain and Ireland, using the defined parameters (a, b, c, d). These results suggest that the model is a reasonable and robust tool for forecasting in bubble economies. Additionally, when applied to commodities experiencing abnormal price increases, the model, utilizing the parameter T, can indicate the intensity of the price surge, as well as pinpoint the timing and rate of peak and trough values. Future research, incorporating precise inflation rates and other relevant economic factors, is expected to yield an even more accurate model. Thus, the proposed model is not only capable of fitting historical price data but also provides a practical tool for identifying and forecasting bubble dynamics in real markets.

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